

**The Power of Knowledge for Action:
*How Young People are Building Local Climate Resilience***

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Abstract

Climate change has become one of the central issues of concern for youth across the globe. From physical protests and rallies to virtual campaigns and manifestoes that demand change, young people are making their own space to influence climate change policies. While some of the youth are digitally connected, with tools to communicate their views to influence world leaders, several others are helping marginalized communities adapt to climate change in their everyday lives by building resilience at the local level to deal with the impacts of climate change., through actions linked to knowledge, learning, and mobilization.

Keywords: Youth, Climate Change, Locally-led Actions, Influence

"You have stolen my childhood and my dreams with your empty words. You're failing us, but young people are starting to understand your betrayal."

(Thunberg, 2019)

Change in weather patterns, with related changes in oceans and the land regionally and globally, is a scientific explanation of climate change. What does "climate change" mean as a lived experience for semi-literate or illiterate individuals living in semi-urban or rural areas, and in the informal settlements in large

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metropolitan cities in the global South? As a local community, excessive or inadequate rainfall in the cropping cycle, water scarcity or non-availability of clean water in homes, erratic temperatures, food spoilage due to increase in pests, insects, heat stress inside their shanty dwellings that lack ventilation, are some of the ways in which they can define their experience of climate change. These experiences affect the future of the young people living in these communities.

In a 2019 survey of 10,000 young people (aged 18-25) in 22 countries across six continents, for 41% of the respondents, climate change was a central issue of concern (Amnesty International, 2019). Greta Thunberg's words have been successful in collectivizing and inspiring adolescents, teenagers and youth from across the globe to fight for their futures. Several of these youth are social media-savvy, digitally connected, with tools to communicate their views to influence world leaders to do something about the climate emergency.

And there are several others, living in and helping marginalized communities adapt to climate change in their everyday lives by building resilience at the local level, through actions linked to knowledge, learning, and mobilization. This requires building the ability, especially of young people, through community programs, to anticipate, prepare for, and respond to catastrophic events and trends related to climate.

Youth in South Asia are using local knowledge for local action

Over the past year, the Participatory Research in Asia (PRIA) Youth team has engaged with youth from South Asian countries to document their narratives of local actions and systematize how local knowledge can be linked with the science of climate change. Youth representatives and leaders from various parts of the world shared their locally-led actions in a series of consultation, organized from November 2020 – January 2021 in run up to the

GOBESHONA Global Conference. Some of these experiences are documented below.

Recurring droughts, dry and warm conditions have become a visible outcome of climate change faced by smaller underserved communities and towns, and treated wastewater in such situations, encouraged as a substitute for natural freshwater, is a relatively difficult and expensive process to be adopted by poorer communities. Lalita Prasada Sripada Srisai, an undergraduate student of agriculture in a university in eastern India, has experimented with using locally produced and available corn cobs to produce a low-cost, eco-friendly method of purifying wastewater. Lalita's journey to bring a "new scientific solution" to the community began with understanding their local practices consumption and disposal of corn cobs. She adapted this lived knowledge to develop a cost-effective, easy-to-replicate method for the community, while she was studying in a school in Koraput district in Odisha.

Erratic temperatures have started impacting human and environmental systems in Myanmar. In the new township areas of Yangon, informal settlements are concentrated in the barren, exposed, open spaces with lack of tree cover. With increased traffic and pollution from factories and other sources, higher levels of heat are generated. This affects the health of the poorer residents of the city. Youth leaders, who play the role of community architects like, Phyo Thura Han, with the support of local community-based organizations, are stepping forward to raise awareness on the issue and to design participatory approaches in building community resilience.

Sameer Ahmad, a social work student from University of Delhi Delhi, is working to achieve responsible consumption and production, included in the UN Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 12 for the efficient management of natural resources. To influence the lifestyle of his peers, Sameer has begun cataloguing simple tips and tricks that can help them adopt sustainable and

responsible ways of living. He also demonstrates these practices to raise awareness and promote healthy living.

Young people raising their voices to influence decision making at the national and global levels

PRIA collectivized the voices of youth from several countries and documented their concerns in *Our Future, Our Voice: A Youth Manifesto on Climate Adaptation*. The manifesto emphasizes the need for multi-stakeholder partnerships and collaborations at the community, regional, national, and global levels where families are also activated as equal stakeholders in contributing to climate adaptation policies. They want opportunities and resources to be made available to young people to participate in local initiatives.

They also demand that climate adaptation strategies be imbibed in the “educational conscience” of schools and higher education institutions, and researchers should use an intersectional lens of caste, class, gender, power, and inequality to understand the impact of climate change on local communities. Through this manifesto, the youth emphasize the need for effective community management in adaptation practices, by providing platforms for vulnerable and indigenous communities to bring their local knowledge, existing practices, concerns, and ideas to be included in the climate change discussions.

From physical protests and rallies to virtual campaigns and manifestoes that demand change, young people are making their own space to influence climate change policies. Their involvement in locally-led actions, using the knowledge and capacities of local communities, holds the potential to build resilience to deal with the impacts of climate change.

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